

HEMATOLOGICAL STRESS AND RENAL DYSFUNCTION FOLLOWING ALCOHOL EXPOSURE IN RATS: A BIOMARKER-BASED ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated alcohol's effects on hematological and renal parameters in rats. The consumption of alcohol has been fundamental to socio-cultural dynamics worldwide. Alcohol has a significant negative impact on kidney function, in addition, it has effects on blood. Standard methods was used in carrying out the FBC, white blood cell differentials, and kidney function indices were assessed. The rats are group, (Groups A–G), showing significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Group B had the highest PCV ($59.33 \pm 0.57\%$), Hb (30.51 ± 0.08 g/dl), RBC (8.72 ± 0.14), MCH (35.37 ± 0.05 pg), and MCHC (51.62 ± 0.35 g/dl), while Group F recorded the lowest PCV ($34.33 \pm 0.57\%$), Hb (11.50 ± 0.23 g/dl), and RBC (4.68 ± 0.40). MCV remained relatively stable (~ 68.47 – 68.91 fL). TWBC was highest in Groups B and G (32.66 ± 0.57) and lowest in Group D (28.33 ± 0.57). Neutrophils peaked in Group F ($44.43 \pm 0.36\%$), while lymphocytes were highest in Group A ($63.50 \pm 5.46\%$) and lowest in Group B ($44.13 \pm 0.81\%$). Platelet counts ranged from 505.66 ± 1.15 to 532.33 ± 1.52 , highest in Group C. Renal dysfunction was most evident in Group G, with elevated urea (31.25 ± 0.02 mg/dl) and creatinine (1.70 ± 0.06 mmol/l). Electrolyte imbalance included hyponatremia in Groups C (78.82 ± 0.14 mEq/L) and G (78.62 ± 0.08 mEq/L), hyperkalemia in Group F (7.30 ± 0.10 mEq/L), and increased bicarbonate in Group D (54.54 ± 0.15 mmol/l). Alcohol administration resulted in significant alterations in erythrocyte indices, immune cell distribution, and electrolyte balance. These findings indicate that alcohol induces hematological stress, immune dysregulation, and renal dysfunction in a dose-dependent and brand-dependent manner.

KEYWORD: Alcohol, renal, heamatology, inflammation and biomarker.

INTRODUCTION

The consumption of alcohol has been fundamental to socio-cultural dynamics worldwide. The 2016 World Health Organization study revealed that more than 43% of the global population aged over 15 years had ingested alcohol in the prior 12 months, (W. H. O. 2018). The Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (2013) indicated that the alcohol consumption rates for men and women were 75.3% and 45.7%, respectively, (Health, 2016). The consumption of alcohol has many effects on health. Notwithstanding its evident adverse health effects, including liver cirrhosis,

cancers, seizures, pancreatitis, and poisoning, previous studies have suggested that light to moderate alcohol consumption may offer specific advantages, such as a reduced risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes, (Yu- Ji et al., 2016).

Acute alcohol intoxication is a harmful clinical condition that can lead to traumatic injuries, impair organ function, and increase morbidity and death rates, (Hu et al., 2013). Moderate alcohol use is cardioprotective, however excessive drinking increases the risk of renal disease by

negatively affecting endothelial function, hence raising the probability of renal injury, (Tanaka et al., 2017).

As a result, alcohol-fed rats demonstrate significant renal dysfunction, interstitial oedema, renal hypertrophy, and increased concentrations of oxidised proteins and lipids in the kidneys, (Tsai et al., 2017). A recent study revealed that rats receiving intravenous ethanol before the start of hemorrhagic shock displayed markedly elevated renal tubular necrosis scores and heightened blood levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines. The kidney is an essential organ that conducts excretory functions as well as synthesising substances that stimulate physiological processes, enhance enzymatic reactions, and aid in immunisation. After ethanol consumption, the kidneys metabolise ethanol and its metabolites, which are subsequently excreted in urine, with urinary concentrations surpassing those seen in blood and liver. The kidney often engages in the formation, preservation, and counter-regulation of complex electrolyte imbalances. Some studies suggest that persistent ethanol intake is not nephrotoxic. The kidney is generally the only critical organ retained in chronic drinkers without significant alcoholic liver disease or hepato-renal syndrome. Nonetheless, chronic alcohol consumption increases blood pressure, which is intrinsically a risk factor for renal dysfunction. Excessive ethanol intake negatively affects renal function. Structural and functional renal abnormalities are frequently reported in infants with foetal alcohol syndrome resulting from prenatal ethanol exposure. This study primarily aimed to investigate the effects of hematological stress and renal dysfunction following alcohol exposure in rats: a biomarker-based assessment.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Animals and Experimental Ethics Protocol

All experimental methods were carried out in compliance with ethical standards and guidelines that are congruent with the ARRIVE Guidelines, as approved. Thirty-Five Wistar rats weighing 150–160 g was obtained from animal house of the Department of Biochemistry, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria, where they were housed under standard condition of temperature ($27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) with twelve hours light/dark periodicity in plastic cages. The rats were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks and were fed ad libitum

during this period, with water and grower mesh feed. Animals were handled throughout the period of study according to institutions guidelines for experiment involving the use of animals.

Experimental design

Thirty-five (35) rats were randomly divided into seven groups, and each group has five (5) rats. Group A served as the control and received only solvent (distilled water). High dose seaman was administered to Group B, C and D received a high dose of 3ml/kg/day of Seaman, Chelsea, and Lord respectively while Group E, F and G received a low dose of 1.5ml/kg/day of Seaman, Chelsea, and Lord respectively. All the animals in each group were weighed before and after the experiment. The route of administration was oral with the aid of orogastric tube.

Study Duration: This study lasted for four weeks (two weeks for acclimatization and two weeks for substance administration. During the four weeks study period, the animals were fed and observed for various behaviours.

Sample Collection At the end of three weeks of administration, the rats were sacrificed by administering chloroform as anaesthesia. Following sacrifice, blood was drawn by heart puncture and collected in simple, sterile, centrifuged bottles to clot. Blood serum was prepared by centrifuging the samples separately and storing them at -20°C until the amounts of serum/homogenate were needed. Standard methods were used to checked for hematological functions and kidney function parameters. The rats were then dissected to harvest the organ and were then fixed immediately in 10% formalin.

Statistical analysis Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for all statistical calculations. Differences were considered probably significant at a P-value of

RESULTS

Effect of Alcohol on Full Blood Count of rats

The effect of graded doses of Seaman, Chelsea, and Lords alcoholic beverages on erythrocytic indices is presented in Table 1. Alcohol exposure produced marked alterations in hematological parameters compared with the control group (A).

Table 1: Effect of Alcohol on Full Blood Count of rats.

Grp	PCV (%)	HB (g/dl)	RBC	MCV (fL)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g/dl)
A	37.33±0.57 ^b	12.46±0.26 ^b	5.34±0.02 ^b	68.91±0.05 ^b	22.86±0.17 ^a	33.33±0.00 ^a
B	59.33±0.57 ^f	30.51±0.08 ^g	8.72±0.14 ^e	68.47±0.10 ^{ab}	35.37±0.05 ^c	51.62±0.35 ^c
C	58.33±0.57 ^{ef}	20.45±0.00 ^f	8.36±0.16 ^{de}	68.50±0.06 ^{ab}	24.36±0.38 ^b	35.62±0.30 ^b
D	54.67±0.57 ^d	18.26±0.26 ^d	7.83±0.24 ^c	68.72±0.16 ^{ab}	22.76±0.18 ^a	33.34±0.01 ^a
E	52.66±0.57 ^c	17.59±0.05 ^c	7.63±0.19 ^c	68.69±0.21 ^{ab}	22.65±0.15 ^a	33.34±0.08 ^a
F	34.33±0.57 ^a	11.50±0.23 ^a	4.68±0.40 ^a	68.53±0.47 ^{ab}	22.68±0.32 ^a	33.35±0.03 ^a
G	57.33±0.57 ^e	18.89±0.05 ^e	8.21±0.11 ^d	68.56±0.05 ^{ab}	22.62±0.32 ^a	33.34±0.01 ^a

Values are mean ± SEM of 3 triplicates. Different superscript letters (e.g., ^a, ^b) indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$; same letters (e.g., ^a) (Duncan's).

Effect of alcohol on White Blood Count Parameters of rats

Leukocytosis and neutrophilia were brought on by alcohol exposure, suggesting an inflammatory reaction. Immune suppression may be indicated by lower lymphocyte counts in high-dose groups. These results are

consistent with reports that alcohol causes oxidative stress and cytokine imbalance, which upset immune homeostasis. Improved lymphocyte levels and normalised leukocyte distribution were observed in low-dose groups, indicating a partial immune recovery.

Tables 2: Effect of alcohol on White Blood Count Parameters of rats.

Grp	TWBC	Platelets	MPV (fL)	Neutrophils (%)	Lymphocytes (%)	Monocytes (%)	Eosinophils (%)	Basophils (%)
A	30.33±0.57 ^b	509.83±0.57 ^a	4.33± 0.57 ^b	37.43± 0.11 ^a	63.50± 5.46 ^c	1.13 ± 0.05 ^a	4.66 ± 0.05 ^d	0.53 ± 0.05 ^a
B	32.66±0.57 ^c	509.3 ± 0.57 ^b	4.80± 0.10 ^a	40.633± 0.57 ^c	44.13± 0.81 ^a	1.37 ± 0.05 ^b	4.26 ± 0.11 ^b	0.86 ± 0.05 ^c
C	30.33±0.57 ^b	532.33 ± 1.52 ^d	3.90± 0.10 ^a	36.73± 0.70 ^e	45.53± 0.30 ^a	1.37± 0.05 ^b	5.13 ± 0.05 ^c	0.63 ± 0.05 ^{ab}
D	28.33±0.57 ^a	505.66 ± 1.15 ^c	4.23± 0.15 ^d	35.76± 0.55 ^d	55.80± 0.10 ^b	1.43± 0.05 ^b	4.70 ± 0.10 ^d	0.56 ± 0.05 ^a
E	28.66±0.57 ^a	512.66 ± 0.57 ^a	4.43± 0.05 ^d	37.43± 0.50 ^c	57.80± 0.10 ^b	1.53± 0.05 ^b	3.76 ± 0.05 ^a	1.33 ± 0.05 ^d
F	30.66±0.57 ^b	507.33±0.57 ^c	4.23± 0.05 ^c	44.43± 0.36 ^b	58.80± 0.10 ^b	1.76± 0.11 ^c	4.26 ± 0.05 ^b	0.76 ± 0.05 ^c
G	32.66±0.57 ^c	522.66 ± 0.57 ^c	4.26± 0.57 ^d	33.23± 0.15 ^c	60.80± 0.10 ^b	1.31± 0.20 ^b	4.53 ± 0.05 ^c	0.63 ± 0.05 ^{bc}

Effect of alcohol on Kidney Function Parameters of rats

Renal biomarkers showed significant dysfunction following alcohol exposure. Elevated urea and creatinine in Group G indicate impaired kidney function.

Electrolyte imbalance, including hyponatremia and hyperkalemia, suggests disruption of renal homeostasis.

Extreme bicarbonate elevation in Group D indicates metabolic alkalosis, while variations across groups reflect acid–base imbalance.

Tables 3: Effect of alcohol on Kidney Function Parameters of rats.

Group	Urea (mg/dl)	CL ⁻ (mEq/L)	Na ⁺ (mEq/L)	K ⁺ (mEq/L)	HCO ₃ ⁻ (mmol/l)	CR (mmol/l)
A	16.07 ± 0.09 ^f	98.08 ± 0.06 ^b	100.30 ± 0.10 ^f	3.23 ± 0.16 ^a	20.15 ± 0.51 ^c	10.07 ± 0.26 ^c
B	15.27 ± 0.06 ^e	95.53 ± 0.33 ^a	99.36 ± 0.23 ^e	3.18 ± 0.35 ^a	19.63 ± 0.47 ^b	10.03 ± 0.31 ^c
C	8.58 ± 0.22 ^a	102.76 ± 0.16 ^d	78.82 ± 0.14 ^b	5.82 ± 0.49 ^d	10.93 ± 0.16 ^a	0.63 ± 0.42 ^a
D	9.28 ± 0.36 ^b	126.55 ± 0.03 ^f	91.64 ± 0.35 ^c	4.44 ± 0.13 ^c	54.54 ± 0.15 ^f	0.50 ± 0.37 ^a
E	10.11 ± 0.00 ^c	118.16 ± 0.57 ^e	44.46 ± 0.35 ^a	3.57 ± 0.96 ^b	24.55 ± 0.06 ^e	0.75 ± 0.19 ^a
F	13.43 ± 0.35 ^d	129.24 ± 0.16 ^g	93.34 ± 0.16 ^d	7.30 ± 0.10 ^e	21.60 ± 0.32 ^d	0.74 ± 0.14 ^a
G	31.25 ± 0.02 ^g	98.60 ± 0.10 ^c	78.62 ± 0.08 ^b	4.69 ± 0.03 ^c	24.54 ± 0.04 ^e	1.70 ± 0.06 ^b

Values are mean ± SEM of 3 triplicates. Different superscript letters (e.g., ^a, ^b) indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$; same letters (e.g., ^a) (Duncan's)

DISCUSSION

The effect of graded doses of Seaman, Chelsea, and Lords alcoholic beverages on erythrocytic indices is presented in Table 1. Alcohol exposure produced marked alterations in hematological parameters compared with the control group (A). Haematological parameters were significantly changed by alcohol exposure. PCV, Hb, and RBC significantly increased in alcohol-treated groups, especially in high-dose (B–D) exposure, according to the results. In comparison to the control group (PCV: 37.33 ± 0.57%; Hb: 12.46 ± 0.26 g/dl; RBC: 5.34 ± 0.02), Group B had the highest PCV (59.33 ± 0.57%), Hb (30.51 ± 0.08 g/dl), and RBC (8.72 ± 0.14), in contrast, group F (Chelsea 3 ml) showed a significant reduction in PCV (34.33 ± 0.57%) and Hb (11.50 ± 0.23 g/dl) compared with control.

This suggests hemoconcentration, most likely as a result of dehydration brought on by alcohol. Ethanol inhibits antidiuretic hormone (ADH), increasing fluid loss and potentially concentrating circulating blood components, (Das et al., 2025).

Group F, on the other hand, displayed lower haematological indices, which may indicate anaemia or erythropoiesis suppression. This dual response suggests that, depending on the dosage and length of exposure, alcohol toxicity may have both stimulatory and suppressive effects.

While elevated MCH and MCHC in Group B indicate increased haemoglobin concentration per cell, potentially as a result of cellular dehydration or oxidative stress, MCV remained relatively constant, indicating normocytic conditions and similar increases in erythrocyte indices following alcohol exposure have been reported by (Gupta et al., 2025), who attributed such changes to oxidative stress and membrane modifications affecting red blood cell stability. And this also is consistent with recent research showing that alcohol increases blood viscosity and upsets fluid balance, (Das et al., 2022). On the other hand, Group F decreased levels of these parameters suggest the possibility of anaemia or bone marrow suppression or hemolysis at higher toxic doses, aligning with findings

from (Olayemi et al., 2021), who reported dose-dependent hematotoxicity following chronic ethanol administration in rats and has been linked to impaired erythropoiesis and chronic alcohol toxicity, (Yokus et al., 2025). The current study shows that exposure to alcohol causes notable changes in rats' haematological and renal systems, with the effects differing depending on the alcohol brand and dose. The dose-dependent effect was further supported by Groups C and G, which also displayed elevated PCV values ($58.33 \pm 0.57\%$ and $57.33 \pm 0.57\%$, respectively). These results are consistent with those of (Yokus et al., 2025), who found that subjects exposed to alcohol had higher haematological parameters as a result of lower plasma volume.

Group F, on the other hand, had significantly lower PCV ($34.33 \pm 0.57\%$), Hb (11.50 ± 0.23 g/dl), and RBC (4.68 ± 0.40), which may indicate bone marrow suppression or anaemia. This corroborates claims that long-term alcohol consumption can affect erythropoiesis. MCV values (68.47 – 68.91 fL) stayed comparatively constant, indicating that red blood cell size did not significantly change. However, Group B had significantly higher levels of MCH and MCHC (35.37 ± 0.05 pg; 51.62 ± 0.35 g/dl), suggesting hyperchromic cells that were probably caused by oxidative stress, Qureshi et al., 2025). While variations in MCH and MCHC suggest changes in haemoglobin concentration within erythrocytes, the comparatively stable MCV values across groups suggest that red blood cell size was not significantly affected. One well-known effect of alcohol metabolism is oxidative stress, which could be the cause of these changes, (Bouajila et al., 2025).

Organ-body weight ratios are typically examined to see if the organ's size has changed in relation to the animal's overall weight; a high ratio has been linked to inflammation, whereas a low ratio has been linked to constriction, (Iboyi and Adebayo, 2021).

Renal function parameters showed marked alterations, confirming alcohol-induced nephrotoxicity. Elevated urea levels, particularly in Group G, indicate impaired renal clearance or increased protein catabolism. The fluctuations in creatinine levels suggest altered glomerular filtration rates, consistent with findings that alcohol affects kidney function through oxidative and inflammatory pathways (Lee et al., 2025).

As shown in Table 2, total white blood cell (TWBC) count increased significantly in groups B and G compared with control, suggesting alcohol-induced inflammatory or immune stimulation. Conversely, groups D and E recorded lower TWBC values. The distribution of immune cells was considerably changed by alcohol exposure. Compared to the control group (30.33 ± 0.57), TWBC rose in Groups B and G (32.66 ± 0.57), suggesting systemic inflammation.

Group F ($44.43 \pm 0.36\%$) and Group B ($40.63 \pm 0.57\%$) had higher neutrophil counts than the control ($37.43 \pm 0.11\%$), indicating an acute inflammatory response, while lymphocyte percentage declined notably in group B ($44.13 \pm 0.81\%$) and C ($45.53 \pm 0.30\%$) compared with control ($63.50 \pm 5.46\%$). This neutrophilia with relative lymphopenia suggests stress-related immune modulation. This is consistent with research showing that alcohol activates the innate immune system (Melamud et al., 2023).

Immunosuppression was indicated by a significant decrease in lymphocytes in Group B ($44.13 \pm 0.81\%$) compared to control ($63.50 \pm 5.46\%$). This decrease demonstrates how alcohol reduces adaptive immunity. Platelet counts varied slightly, with Group C having the highest value (532.33 ± 1.52), which may indicate a stress response or platelet activation. Variations in MPV also point to altered platelet function. Neutrophilia and lymphocytopenia were found in the white blood cell profile, suggesting an inflammatory response combined with immunosuppression. This pattern aligns with findings that alcohol suppresses adaptive immune responses while boosting innate immune activity (Melamud et al., 2023). Reduced lymphocytes indicate weakened immune function, whereas an increase in neutrophils indicates acute stress or inflammation.

There were significant drops in sodium (hyponatraemia) and increases in potassium (hyperkalaemia) indicated an electrolyte imbalance. These alterations are frequently linked to alcohol toxicity and show poor renal regulation of electrolytes, (Zheng et al., 2024). Acid-base disorders, such as metabolic acidosis and alkalosis in various groups, are further suggested by the differences in bicarbonate levels.

The observed variations between alcohol brands also emphasise the possible influence of additives and alcohol composition on toxicity levels. A dose-dependent relationship was confirmed by the generally more noticeable effects of high-dose exposure.

Significant disruption was found in kidney function parameters. Group G had the highest urea levels (31.25 ± 0.02 mg/dl) compared to the control group (16.07 ± 0.09 mg/dl), suggesting either increased protein breakdown or impaired renal clearance.

The majority of treated groups had lower creatinine levels (e.g., Group D: 0.50 ± 0.37 mmol/l), but Group G had higher levels (1.70 ± 0.06 mmol/l), indicating varying renal impairment. These results align with the findings of (Lee et al., 2025), who documented kidney dysfunction caused by alcohol.

There was a clear electrolyte imbalance in Group E, sodium levels dramatically decreased (44.46 ± 0.35 mEq/L), suggesting hyponatraemia. Group F had elevated potassium (7.30 ± 0.10 mEq/L), a sign of

hyperkalaemia, Group F had higher levels of chloride (129.24 ± 0.16 mEq/L).

The levels of bicarbonate varied greatly in Group C had low levels of metabolic acidosis (10.93 ± 0.16 mmol/L), Group D had a high level of metabolic alkalosis (54.54 ± 0.15 mmol/L).

These results support reports that link alcohol consumption to electrolyte imbalances and renal tubular dysfunction.^[16]

Generally, high-dose groups (B–D) displayed more severe changes than low-dose groups (E–G). On the other hand, Group G (low dose) exhibited severe urea elevation, indicating toxicity specific to the brand. This suggests that alcohol composition including additives and ethanol concentration may affect toxicity in addition to dosage. The differential responses among beverage brands may be attributable to variations in alcohol concentration, additives, or other chemical constituents. High-dose Chelsea (3 ml) produced the most pronounced hematological suppression, indicating potential higher toxicity at increased concentration.

Alcohol-induced nephrotoxicity was confirmed by significant changes in renal function parameters. Increased protein catabolism or poor renal clearance are indicated by elevated urea levels, especially in Group G. The variations in creatinine levels point to changed glomerular filtration rates, which is in line with research showing alcohol impairs kidney function via inflammatory and oxidative pathways (Bouajila *et al.*, 2024).

CONCLUSION

Alcohol exposure causes significant hematological stress, immune dysregulation, and renal dysfunction in rats. These effects are dose-dependent and influenced by the type of alcohol consumed. The study highlights the potential health risks associated with alcohol consumption and underscores the importance of monitoring hematological and renal biomarkers.

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